

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4095254

Vidyankur XXII/1 Jan-June 2020, ISSN 2249-1503 | 23-35

Being Human in Scientific and Technological Era: Reaching to the Higher Level of Consciousness?

Nirmal Kullu SJ

Vidyajyoti College of Theology, Delhi

Abstract: Today the human beings are facing the identity problem of self, others and the world as well. The scientific age has progressed rapidly and discovered and manufactured sophisticated machine and electronic gadgets which have made our life very easy. At the same time priorities over machine than human has confused human being at this juncture of life. The modern era has downed with artificial intelligence which seems to subdue human intelligence. It raises many questions for humanity concerning their survival, existence, domination, and identity. Human values seem to be in danger of being extinct or replaced by modern gadgets. This paper tries to synthesize humanity and artificial intelligence and tries to show that science and humanity are not contradicting to each other but together growing towards higher level of consciousness.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Natural Intelligence, Easy Flipping, Framing Nature, Embedded Self, Humanity, Relationality, Rationality, Spirituality.

Introduction

Human person is a unique being on this planet. He is endowed with wisdom, knowledge, intrinsic values of love, kindness, generosity, and service, feelings for and with others. All these values unite human species together as species having consciousness greater than other species in the world. Science has proved that matters in a different form can render excellent service to humanity. Artificial intelligence has played a vital role in this scientific age to achieve unimaginable dreams. Therefore, being human for the human person has become a great challenge today in this scientific and technological age.

The Body, Mind and Soul of Being Human

Being human in the modern era is understood more simply by the elaboration of the given phase 'Being human in Scientific Era'. It can be segregated in three parts, mainly 'Being human and human being' is the first, secondly – 'in scientific', and the third – 'era' that is the timeline. Let me raise a question – who is a human being? To respond to this question, I would say that human being is a biological being, a physical reality as an existing person on this planet. Therefore, it implies a human person has a *body*, *mind* and *soul*. So, a human being is combination of three existing realities – a body, which sustains the physical reality of being alive and does all the physical activities as a human person. The second part of the human being is the mind which is responsible for the rationality of human being, knowing faculty of our being. The third part is the soul; we also associate it with our experiencing faculty. The soul is implanted by God during the conception in mother's womb is the belief of the believers. The atheists don't believe in the existence of soul in human being.

What does being human imply?

We imply it is a *human person, fully alive with rationality, relationality and spirituality.*

Human rationality is that aspect of humanity through which a person can think, imagine, dream, give articulation to his thinking in language form, express this thinking through art and culture, dance, music etc. Relationality is all

that a person can relate to oneself, to divine, others, environment and to the entire universe. Spirituality is that aspect of human person through which he experiences finitude in his being and tends towards infinity, beyond finitude. It is a way of life based on certain values. Being human means all the qualities and value system a person can have in his life which distinguishes the person from other being on this earth. A person who knows good and bad and has the freedom to choose good for all and for everyone could be considered as being human. The second part is 'in scientific or modern' which means material development where electronic equipment, machines are produced and machine intelligence or artificial intelligence is used for their operation.

This essay shows the challenge to be truly human and appreciate the development of science and artificial intelligence and tries to synthesize both towards higher level of consciousness.

The third part of the topic is "Era" means the timeline of existence. From the scientific point of view, we understand the beginning of the existence of the universe from the big bang theory. Therefore, our universe is 20 billion years old. Humanity is only 4 million years old in this timeline. "Era" indicates a particular time period of our existing where something has happened during that period. Therefore, it is the time period of the starting of artificial intelligence and scientific growth and its dominion over the human being. Artificial intelligence is the machine intelligence or the

intelligence demonstrated by the machine which is in contrast to the natural intelligence performed by human mind. Artificial intelligence (AI) has progressed so rapidly that it has emerged successfully in the area of knowledge representation, problem-solving, reasoning, learning, planning, natural language processing, motion and manipulation, perception and other areas as well. Its advancement can be seen to the depths of the sea to the height of the universe, even the unknown planets are no more hidden from the knowledge of the human being through the help of the Artificial Intelligence. The entire earth is positively and negatively affected by this intelligence. Life of human has become very comfortable, easy, effective, organized, compact and productive. The impact of artificial intelligence is so much in our lives today that it becomes very difficult to live without it. In any sector of life, be it personal, social, relational, official or governmental it has become the part of us without which the system seems to collapse or seems to shut down our life itself. Therefore, it is appropriate to put forward the views on “Being human in scientific Era”.

Self-Understanding

How do I understand myself in the Modern Era? I, as a human being on this planet, have a unique identity. I am not a machine, nor a plant, neither an animal but a human being, having consciousness greater than other existing things and lives on the earth. Therefore human being is a unique being, valuable being and has inviolable dignity. We are aware of our knowing and willing. Freedom plays an important role in our life. Human experiences tell us that we belong to nature but at the same time we are radically different from it. Therefore, we come to this earth with a purpose, dreams, hopes, aspirations and full of life.

We experience contingency and finitude and live between birth and death. Human beings do not bring themselves into existence and they do not have the power to keep themselves into existence. Everywhere we notice beginning and end. In this world, nothing seems to be permanent. At the same time human being experiences in their depth a longing for and a movement towards transcendence. Therefore, our goal is not ourselves and our meaning is not within us. We seek to go beyond ourselves in freedom, knowing and in loving. In this journey of living and progress the artificial intelligence helps human being to understand the meaning of life better and who they are in a relationship with the matter, with the self, with others and with the universe.

Looking at the progress and the web of artificial intelligence that has spread over the earth and the universe, it often triggers us to think – ‘will the artificial intelligence overcome human being’? I would reflect it this way that artificial intelligence is the creation of the human mind and human being is not the creation of artificial intelligence. The evolution theory of Charles Darwin highlights the progress of life from the matter to cells, plants, animals, Homo sapiens and ultimately this matter reaches the higher level of consciousness in human being. This human being tries to understand the functions of matter in form of machines, electronic gadgets, computers, sensors, detectors, other equipment used in different platform of life through commands, programming, algorithms, arithmetic calculation, binary numbers, flipping property of electron and sense of the matter and non-matter objects. They use it for the betterment of human life. Therefore the one who creates is always greater than the created one. Each individual human possesses a unique and inviolable dignity. The value of a human being doesn’t depend on the possession of material goods. The value of the human person is not possession, not doing aspects but it is very much being aspects. What he/she

becomes in the process of doing and achieving in life is more significant in the real-life scenario. Human being also has a social dimension which is the intrinsic quality in them. This social dimension comes from very much being born as a human in a family with a mother and having the father which is the first felt realization of human society. Therefore, we can't imagine a human being getting replaced by artificial intelligence. If we look at the human being only as an object on this earth, they exist only for the work and neglect the very aspects of unique and inviolable dignity, their preciousness in the society, then we will be missing the track and this artificial intelligence will take over the human being. We find in the history that human beings were treated as an object in many parts of the world when slavery was very much prominent in society.

When we think about the social dimension of a human being, the concept of relationship plays a very significant role in life which distinguishes us from other being to some extent. We are social being so we need the relationship, communication, human touch, human solidarity, celebration, dance, sympathy, tolerance, understanding each other, collaboration, friendship and all that human experiences which touches our hearts and revives, energizes and gives hope to live life meaningfully. Artificial intelligence has enhanced our socializing process. Now the distance of the world is no more unreachable, families and persons living in a different continent are no more apart from each other but very much known to each and every one. You can travel from one end of the world to the other end within a day. You can converse with the person living in a different country by looking at him through social media. Transportation, travelling, communication gadgets, networking webs etc. have made our socialization process very quick and rapid

and within the fraction of second, we can do everything. The whole world has become one home, in our Indian tradition it is understood as *vashudhev kutumbkam*. I quote from the book *Teilhard de Chardin and the Mystery of Christ* by Christopher F. Mooney (1968), “The peak of ourselves, the acme of our originality, is not our individuality but our person; and according to the evolutionary structure of the world, we can only find our person by uniting together.” The sad reality is that we have failed to be a true human being in the process of socialization. The artificial intelligence which is helpful for us to become the extension of our being, part of ourselves. Machines, mobile, electronic gadgets have occupied my being than my family members and my neighbour next to my door. It seems to us that we are becoming less human by the use of artificial intelligence and neglecting our human values. We have harmed not only ourselves but to the birds, creatures, and eco-system by the overuse of modern gadgets. The waves generated by the use of electronic gadgets especially mobile have destroyed nominal life form. Our life seems to be very difficult without this AI but at the same time it has brought many inconveniences to human life and the environment.

There are positive and negative impacts of AI on the growing population especially the employment of the youth today. The quality and efficiency of work have rapidly increased. The adequate example for this is Huoshenshan hospital in China for the coronavirus patients were made ready within 10 days. At the emergency time, AI has really become a blessing and helpful for people. The whole wealth of India is accumulated by only a few people, which are also the cause of unemployment. India has sent the people to the moon (Chandrayan mission), launched many satellites, made the bullet train, trying to make a driverless car, these are all the advancement of AI but these have taken away the employment of the people. The jobs of hundreds of people are taken by one

JCB for the construction of the road and buildings which causes unemployment.

Challenges to Being Human in the Scientific Era

The challenges that are brought by the artificial intelligence could be in the area of reasoning, problem solving, knowledge presentation, social intelligence and general intelligence. Besides these, I would like to highlight some other challenges as digitalization, time of capturing reality, human existence and human relationship.

Today the entire world is digitalized. All the works are done by digital objects. Human seems to be digitalizing self through the use of all gadgets which is giving him the realization that artificial intelligence is the extension of self. By the manufacturing of robotic human and its works and all other developments of the machine, humans are confused about their potentiality and identity of being human. Advancement of artificial intelligence is surely a blessing for us at the same time science has reached to the age where human have made lots of destructive weapons. A powerful atomic bomb can destroy the entire earth within a fraction of time. If a person having this power goes out of his mind, then no one can stop him from using this destructive weapon. The time is in his hand to capture the entire world. Similarly with the people in the plane which can be hijacked with those responsible persons for destroying others. One of the leading scientists of our time Steven Hawking had rightly expressed his concerns about human existence saying that if the human being has to continue to exist then we need to send some into other planets. We also see the threat to the earth due to the rapid change of climate. We could probably guess after 50 years

the earth temperature will rise more than 80 degree Celsius and survival of life will be really question mark. Incurable and new deceases like cancer, skin decease, coronavirus, etc. threatening and taking away human lives raise questions about our existence. All these are the indirect effect of uncontrolled use of artificial intelligence. Human authentic relationship is in danger today. Artificial intelligence and electronic gadgets have become the centre of human relationship today. We walk side by side but the distance is too far that we don't even look at the person and talk to him instead we are busy talking to someone who is in another country or place. It might be right to say that a child who is born today is a digital child because the child is exposed to artificial intelligence as natural part of its growth.

The Humanity and Science Growing Towards Higher Consciousness

Some of the ways, we can reach a higher consciousness may be the following:

Easy flipping: One of the most important areas where scientists have contributed enormously for the advancement of artificial intelligence is reducing the size of matter in order to increase its property and store more information. Matter acts in its nucleus level and performs better work than ever before. The magnetic property of the flipping of the spin electron creates vast change in the property of matter itself which are used for the storing of data and information. Similarly, human beings have to flip easily. They have to reduce in size that is not physical but 'ego' in order to create more space in their being for others and for humanity. They need to act in nucleus level that is human heart so that whole humanity becomes their own and work not for oneself but for everyone. It is not in the

aspects of domination and lordship on the other but equality and dignity for humanity must be emphasized and practised.

Embedded nature: For the better functioning of material used in technology which we say artificial intelligence, material scientists are embedding two or more different materials into one and coming out with new material with completely different properties. This technology is taking the world forward much faster in this artificial intelligence. Here the social aspect of the human being comes to be exercised and learned from artificial intelligence. The human being needs to embed together, putting the mind and heart together and experience a new being, that is a new society which will function better for human and creation and grow to a higher level of consciousness. Materials don't say that I am aluminium, silicon, arsenic; we can't come together because we have different property. In the same way human being in spite of having a different ideology, different culture and tradition, practising different faith might come together to form a new human society where humanity should take priority than other things and ideas. This calls for the change of horizon and vision. As individual and social being you have dignity and worth as a human being.

Framing self: Everything, where the artificial intelligence is used, is framed beautifully from the outside. This framing is to protect the main functioning part from corrosion, outer reaction, and danger and to serve the purpose for which it is manufactured. This also serves the esthetic sense of beauty for those who purchase it. Today human being needs the frame for oneself. This frame for a human being can be divided into three levels. The first level is clothing, housing which is the basic need for the

human being. The second level of framing self is society, in which human being finds one-self as dignified, valued, precious and in relation with the fellow human being. The third level of framing self is the values the human being have in their heart. These values are love, forgiveness, kindness, care, compassion, justice, peace, mercy, harmony, equality, liberty, fraternity and all those values which promote life. The third level framing serves the purpose of second and the first level framing and together it serves the purpose for which we are created. This elevates oneself into the realm of experience which moulds human's heart, and in return, human begins to act for good of all.

Becoming the prism of life: Prism is a glass in which white light falls and disperses into its seven constitutive colors. The beauty is not seen in the single beam of white light but when it falls in prism and disperses then the beauty of spectrum is admirable. Artificial intelligence has used to understand the phenomenon of light, travelling of waves in different angles, propagation of messages through these waves in medium and vacuum and its speed in all mediums. The human being needs to become prism of life. The singularity of the human being is its humanity. The colour, caste, languages, food, belief, nationality are all the different colours of the same humanity. The beauty lies in its different colours of humanity. Diversity in being human opens the door of ever nonstop evolution than stagnant homogeneity of being human.

Being human in scientific age urges humanity to be sensitive to the lives on earth and the non-living materials as well.

Conclusion

Being human in scientific age urges humanity to be sensitive to the lives on earth and the non-living materials as well. The development of science and the birth of Artificial intelligence make us alert that the rhythm of nature should not be controlled and manipulated but it has to be respected and cooperated by a human being. Science has helped humanity to achieve unimaginable dreams, making robotic human, assisted humanity to expand their life through the medical facility, and provided test-tube baby. AI has helped scientists to achieve long-awaited theory that is the detection of the gravitational wave through LIGO. AI has even reached to the stage where a person can keep all his possessions, money, and bank account in a chip and insert it in his body and he can just scan it to get money from the bank. We need to strike balance somewhere between AI and being human and follow the principle which says – ‘as far as AI helps us to be truly human we must use it and make it part of us but the moment it becomes a hindrance for us to be truly human one must become aware of it’. The artificial intelligence must serve the progress, promotion of human life and expansion of human life with all its beauty. Finally, humanity is growing to the higher level of consciousness along with material reality provided he/she sees everything the extension of self and gives due respect and care for the living and non-living reality

References

- Skinner, B. F. (2014). *Science and Human Behavior*. New York: Free Press.
- Anwer, J. S. (2015). Artificial Intelligence and its role in near Future. *Journal of Latex Class Files*, Vol. 14, No. 8, 11.

- Bostrom Nick, Jan-Kyrre Berg Olsen, Evan Sclinger, Soren Riis. (2009). *The Future of Humanity. New Waves in Philosophy of Technology*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mooney, Christopher F. (1968). *Teilhard de Chardin and Mystery of Christ*. New York: Image Books.
- Max, T. (2017). *Life 3.0: Being Human in the age of Artificial Intelligence*. New York.
- Pamela, M. (2004). *Machines Who Think*. New Maxico: A K Peters, Ltd.

Nirmal Kullu is the student of Theology, at Vidyajyoti College of Theology, Delhi. He belongs to Hazaribag Jesuit Province, Jharkhand. He has done his M.Sc. (Physics) from St. Joseph's College, Bengaluru and B.Ph. from Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth Pune. Email: kullusjn@gmail.com

Received Nov 23, 2019: Accepted Dec 2, 2019: Words: 3540

licenses/by/4.0/).

© by the authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).